

Flexible Aircraft Wings with Fuel Slosh Effects

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Due to the use of highly flexible materials, aircraft wings can deform significantly during their operation due to atmospheric turbulence or a gust. Such deformation has the potential to induce significant sloshing of the fuel inside the wing. This phenomenon is of interest in the field of aircraft design since the dynamic loading of a sloshing fuel tank can have a significant impact on the structural dampening of the wing, potentially leading to an exploitable reduction in structural loads due to the energy of the slosh.

The interaction between a flexible wing and the sloshing fuel tank is complex and challenging to numerically model due to its nonlinear, multiphysics and multiphase nature. In this study, we will outline a model capable of predicting this complex flow. Furthermore, we will investigate the impact of excitation amplitude on the geometry of the fuel-tank due to the sloshing dynamics. We have employed a highly scalable open-source multiphase fluid-structure interaction (FSI) framework, developed by the authors, to simulate the elastic sloshing aircraft wing and will present the results. The FSI framework uses a partitioned approach with an Aitken's implicit coupling methodology [1] to achieve a tight and stable coupling for multiphase FSI. The Multiscale Universal Interface (MUI) general code coupling library [2] is employed as the interface between fluid and structural domains. The computational fluid dynamics (CFD) package OpenFOAM [3] and the computational structure mechanics (CSM) solver FEniCS [4] are employed for the fluid and structural domains, respectively. The FSI simulation framework shows a good performance in HPC environments for simulating complex and challenging cases [5, 6].

In the present study, a simplified, beam-like aeroplane wing model is used to represent an elastic aircraft wing. The beam has a free-tip at one end and is fixed at the other. A fuel-tank with liquid fuel is embedded inside the beam. An external force, which linearly increases with time, is applied to the free tip of the beam for a fixed period of time, at which point the external force is removed to let the system oscillate freely with an excitation amplitude. Different excitation amplitudes will be achieved, and results shown, by varying the magnitude of external forces. Aircraft fuel tanks are typically compartmentalised. Different numbers of baffled regions within the tank will be simulated. Our results will be compared and analysed among different working conditions.

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